

Research Article

EZ.BAH Building Simplified: Game-Based Learning Activities for Building Services

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Abstract: *The EZ.BAH Building Simplified tool addresses the challenges of teaching building services, a field that combines complex technical concepts with hands-on experience requirements. Traditional educational methods in this area often need help to engage students fully and promote long-term knowledge retention. EZ.BAH Building Simplified provides a solution through an interactive, game-based approach that enhances active learning, empowering students to take charge of their education and retain critical concepts more effectively. The tool's structure promotes collaboration, with students working in teams to solve building services problems, thereby developing critical skills in communication, time management, and role assignment. These skills mirror real-world project settings, making the tool highly relevant for future professionals. Beyond immediate educational benefits, EZ.BAH Building Simplified has broader potential applications in other technical fields where engagement and concept mastery are crucial. Future enhancements to the tool include digital integrations through virtual or augmented reality, which would make it accessible remotely and support education in resource-constrained settings. Additionally, content updates incorporating the latest building services technologies and sustainability practices will ensure that EZ.BAH Building Simplified remains aligned with industry standards. This continuous evolution strengthens its educational impact and highlights its commercialization potential as a versatile, adaptable learning tool applicable across technical disciplines, addressing current and future industry needs.*

Keywords: building services; active learning; game-based approach.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Teaching building services presents several challenges due to the complexity, technical nature, and multidisciplinary aspects. The subject, building services, involves highly technical content, such as understanding complex mechanical and electrical systems, system design, energy calculations, and compliance with safety standards and regulations. This can be overwhelming, especially for students with limited engineering or technical backgrounds (Alanne, 2016). However, with the right strategies and tools, educators can empower themselves to make learning more innovative and engaging (Ilbeigi et al., 2023; Jayalath & Esichaikul, 2022). As a hands-on subject, students often need more direct experience, especially in environments where practical resources are limited. Without adequate

exposure to natural systems and components, it is difficult for students to grasp concepts like system installation or troubleshooting fully.

Building services integrate several disciplines, including mechanical, electrical, plumbing, civil engineering, and architecture, to ensure that the systems and equipment used to construct a building make it comfortable, functional, and safe for its occupants. This interdisciplinary nature can be challenging, as students need to understand how each system affects others, from energy consumption to system design. The building services industry constantly evolves with new technologies such as intelligent systems, energy-efficient designs, and green building practices. Keeping up with these advancements and teaching them effectively can be difficult for educators and students. Students often need help to visualize the hidden nature of building services systems, such as electrical conduits, plumbing pipes, or HVAC ducts, since these components are usually concealed within walls, floors, or ceilings.

Building services can sometimes seem tedious or less engaging than other aspects of construction, such as structural design or architecture, particularly when the theoretical or calculation-heavy content dominates the teaching approach. However, by making the subject more engaging, educators can inspire students to see the immediate relevance of what they are learning, mainly when it involves theory-heavy content, complex calculations, or regulatory compliance (Shareef & Farivarsadri, 2020; Cheong et al., 2014). This inspiration can create a more interactive and enjoyable student experience (Adams, 2019).

This paper introduces *EZ.BAH Building Simplified*, a unique method for learning building services. It enhances student engagement, motivation, and understanding by integrating game-like elements into teaching and learning. By employing interactive methods, challenges, and rewards, *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* enhances the learning process and transforms it into a more engaging, immersive, and enjoyable experience.

In the classroom, *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* plays a crucial role in increasing student engagement. By incorporating elements such as leaderboards, points, badges, and levels, students become more actively involved in the learning process and stay motivated to progress through the material. It also helps to enhance the student's understanding of the complex systems in building services. More importantly, *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* promotes student collaboration by encouraging group tasks and interdisciplinary projects. This mirrors the teamwork required in the construction and building services industries and inspires students to work together.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* is a game-based learning approach designed to teach building services concepts in an engaging, interactive, and team-oriented environment. The method transforms traditional learning into a hands-on experience that fosters collaboration, critical thinking, and a deeper understanding of complex mechanical, electrical, and plumbing systems.

2.1 Key Features of the *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* Method and Material

1. **Point-Based System:** Students collect points based on the accuracy, creativity, and speed of their answers to building services problems. This motivates them to think critically and act quickly, making learning an engaging game.
2. **Teamwork and Collaboration:** Students work in small teams (3-4 members), fostering a collaborative environment where they solve problems of building services together. This

approach helps students develop communication, leadership, and problem-solving skills essential for real-world applications in the construction industry.

3. **Module-Based Progression:** The game progresses through various modules, starting with basic concepts like water resources and advancing to more complex tasks, such as integrating mechanical and electrical systems in more significant buildings. As students complete each task, they "level up" to unlock more advanced modules, providing a sense of accomplishment and keeping the learning experience fresh and challenging.
4. **Badges and Certificates:** Badges or certificates are awarded for mastering specific topics (e.g., water sources, water distribution systems, sewerage treatment systems). These rewards incentivise consistent efforts and engagement. Displaying achievements in group chats or Google Classroom motivates students to collect as many badges as possible.
5. **Leaderboard and Point Tracking:** A points system tracks team progress. Students earn points for completing tasks or answering questions from flashcards. A leaderboard displayed in the group chat or Google Classroom fosters friendly competition, encouraging teams to strive for improvement.
6. **Building Manager Role:** Each team designates a "Building Manager" responsible for managing time and keeping track of answers. This role adds an extra layer of organisation and accountability while teaching students time management and leadership.
7. **Flashcard-Based Questioning:** The game relies on flashcards that present questions or instructions on building services topics such as mechanical, electrical, or plumbing systems. The building manager keeps the answers, allowing for a structured and interactive way to test knowledge.
8. **Two-Group Game Structure:** The class is divided into teams of 3-4 members, with two groups (Group 1 and Group 2) playing against each other. One group presents flashcards, and the other must answer as many questions as possible within a 10-minute. After the time limit, the groups switch roles. This format promotes active engagement and fast-paced learning.
9. **Points Calculation:** After both groups have completed their rounds, the Building Manager reviews and calculates points based on correct answers. Each correct answer earns 2 points, and the group with the most points is declared the winner.

2.2 *The Benefits of EZ.BAH Building Simplified*

1. **Active Learning:** This method engages students in active learning by encouraging them to solve real-world building services problems in a competitive setting.
2. **Reinforced Understanding:** Students reinforce their knowledge of complex systems like HVAC, plumbing, and electrical installations by answering questions and solving tasks in a team-based environment.
3. **Motivation through Rewards:** Badges, certificates, and leaderboards add a sense of achievement and motivate students to keep improving.

The *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* method enhances classroom engagement and encourages students to work together, think critically, and apply their theoretical knowledge practically and interactively. It effectively gamifies the learning of building services, turning what could be a challenging subject into a fun, collaborative, and rewarding experience.

3. FINDINGS

EZ.BAH Building Simplified, a tool that merges learning with play, has shown its effectiveness in making complex topics fun and interactive for students. This approach deepens student engagement and fosters active participation and collaboration, making the learning process more exciting and intriguing for educators.

Tables 1 to 3 visually showcase the results from specific modules—Water Sources, Water Supply, and Hot Water Supply Systems—highlighting the positive impact of *EZ.BAH Building Simplified*. The data from these modules proves the method's success in enhancing students' comprehension.

Table 1. The Water Sources Module

Q	Question	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
1	Water resources include lakes, rivers, oceans or water, and etc.	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE
2	In the water cycle, it is the process by which water vapor in the air changes into liquid water.	Condensation	Condensation	Condensation	Condensation
3	Approximately 97% of the world's water is stored in the oceans as saltwater.	TRUE	TRUE	FALSE	TRUE
4	Water in its gaseous form is called	air	air	water vapor	air
5	Plants breathe oxygen...	water vapor cooling to form clouds	water heating up and rising again	water vapor cooling to form clouds	water vapor cooling to form clouds
6	Liquid water forms into gas and rises into the air in...	evaporation	evaporation	evaporation	evaporation
7	What two elements make up water?	Hydrogen and oxygen	Hydrogen and oxygen	Hydrogen and oxygen	Hydrogen and oxygen
8	When water is heated in the ocean by the sun and turns into water vapor.	evaporation	evaporation	evaporation	evaporation
9	What happens during evaporation?	Water changes from liquid to vapor due to heating	Water changes from liquid to vapor due to heating	Water changes from liquid to vapor due to heating	Water changes from liquid to vapor due to heating
10	What happens during precipitation?	The water concentrated in the clouds begins to fall	The water concentrated in the clouds begins to fall	The water concentrated in the clouds begins to fall	The water concentrated in the clouds begins to fall

Table 2. The Water Supply Module

Q	Question	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
1	Pumps regulate water pressure and flow direction along the way.	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE
2	This distribution system usually used when distribution areas located at the lower level.	Gravity Method	Pump and Gravity Method	Pump Method	Pump and Gravity Method
3	This distribution system usually used when distribution areas higher than the main source.	Pump Method	Gravity Method	Pump Method	Gravity Method
4	This distribution system is the most common system used since it is economical and efficient.	Gravity Method	Pump and Gravity Method	Pump and Gravity Method	Pump and Gravity Method
5	The distribution pipelines should be located above the main line.	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE
6	It is suitable for cities with rectangular layouts, where the water mains and branches are laid in rectangles. This statement refers to distribution network of	Grid train system	Grid train system	Ring system	Grid train system
7	The disadvantage of using ring system is	Complicated piping layout	Complicated piping layout	Complicated piping layout	Complicated piping layout
8	The maintenance cost for gravity systems might frequently more expensive than a pump system.	False	False	False	False
9	Advanced piping systems is sometimes called a tree system.	True	True	True	True
10	A _____ piping system is a water distribution piping network that is laid out in a predetermined fashion with piping usually increasing in size as the distance increases from the source of supply.	True	Radial	True	Radial
11	The distribution main should be considered in designing the distribution method.	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE

Table 3. The Hot Water Supply Systems Module

Q	Question	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
1	What type of device is used?	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
2	Hot water supply system consists of several hot water supply systems and hot water supply system.	True	True	True	True
3	The expansion of the system is caused by the heat.	True	True	True	True
4	The type of expansion used in the piping system for hot water.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
5	The hot water supply system is used in hot water supply.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
6	The water supply is caused by the heat.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
7	Hot water supply system consists of several hot water supply systems, and hot water supply.	True	True	True	True
8	The type of hot water supply system is used in hot water supply.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
9	Expansion of water supply system is caused by the heat.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
10	Expansion of water supply system is caused by the heat.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
11	Expansion of water supply system is caused by the heat.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
12	Expansion of water supply system is caused by the heat.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
13	Expansion of water supply system is caused by the heat.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
14	Expansion of water supply system is caused by the heat.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
15	Expansion of water supply system is caused by the heat.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
16	Expansion of water supply system is caused by the heat.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
17	Expansion of water supply system is caused by the heat.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
18	Expansion of water supply system is caused by the heat.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
19	Expansion of water supply system is caused by the heat.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve
20	Expansion of water supply system is caused by the heat.	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve	Expansion Valve

The game-based format makes learning more enjoyable and significantly improves students' understanding of technical topics in building services. The approach promotes collaboration and reinforces critical concepts by incorporating interactive activities, team-based problem-solving, and immediate feedback, enhancing knowledge retention.

With its practical, hands-on nature, this blended approach to learning and play has significantly improved students' academic performance, as evidenced by higher grades. This reassures stakeholders about the effectiveness of *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* enables students to grasp challenging concepts more effectively, transforming the learning experience into educational and enjoyable.

Figure 1 displays the grade distribution for two student cohorts (2023 and 2024). A clear improvement is observed, with the 2024 batch showing remarkable grade enhancement, which directly correlates with the implementation of *EZ.BAH Building Simplified*. This significant improvement is compelling evidence of the method's success in enhancing students' comprehension and engagement with the course content, instilling confidence in stakeholders about the tool's effectiveness.

Figure 1. Final Exam Grades

4. DISCUSSION

The implementation of *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* as a game-based learning tool, is a dynamic shift in teaching building services, a traditionally complex and technical subject. This approach to integrating play with learning has been proven to be engaging and academically beneficial, as evidenced by the improvement of student performance.

Firstly, this learning tool will enhance engagement and motivation. The game-based structure of *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* encourages students to engage more actively with the material. Traditional lecture formats often lead to passive learning, especially with complex topics, but game-based learning shifts this dynamic by creating a competitive yet collaborative environment. The feedback loop created by points, levels, and badges motivates students to keep progressing, which may account for the increased enthusiasm and engagement noted in the classroom. This format keeps students focused on learning objectives while enjoying the process, an essential aspect of maintaining consistent academic effort.

Secondly, this tool has improved students' understanding and retention. Data from Tables 1 to 3 provides concrete evidence of improved understanding in specific modules such as Water Sources, Water Supply, and Hot Water Supply Systems. By structuring learning into manageable levels and modules, *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* allows students to build on their knowledge progressively, ensuring they have a solid grasp of foundational concepts before moving to more complex ones. The hands-on, interactive nature of the activities reinforces understanding as students apply theoretical knowledge to real-life problem-solving scenarios. Immediate feedback from peers and instructors and team-based problem-solving further help reinforce core concepts, leading to better knowledge retention.

Thirdly, it has a significant impact on academic performance. The analysis of grades between the 2023 and 2024 student cohorts shows a significant improvement, suggesting the implementation of *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* has had a positive academic impact. This improvement can be attributed to EZ's practical applied approach. *BAH Building Simplified* allows students to experience building services

concepts in action. This shift from theory to practice is critical for complex subjects like building services. It enables students to connect textbook knowledge and real-world applications, resulting in a deeper understanding and more robust problem-solving skills. These factors likely contributed to the overall grade improvements observed in the 2024 cohort.

Fourthly, this tool has encouraged collaborative learning and enhanced skill development. *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* promotes collaborative learning by organising students into teams to work on challenges, fostering essential communication, teamwork, and leadership skills. The role of the Building Manager and point-based competition between groups incentivise students to take on responsibilities and engage actively. This collaboration mirrors real-world project settings, where interdisciplinary collaboration is essential, particularly in construction and building services. The teamwork deepens students' understanding and prepares them for future professional environments.

Finally, this tool allows for the scalability and versatility of the method - the game-based learning approach as seen in *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* is scalable and could be applied to other technical fields or complex subjects beyond building services. The flexible structure, which uses flashcards, points, and badges, can be customised to suit different learning objectives and topics - future applications of *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* could include exploring the use of digital platforms to track progress, enhance accessibility and expand its impact. Furthermore, as building services continuously evolve with technology and sustainability requirements, *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* could adapt its content, integrating new industry trends and practices to keep the learning experience relevant and up-to-date.

5. CONCLUSION

The discussion around *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* highlights its innovative approach to enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes in a challenging field like building services, where complex technical concepts and the need for hands-on experience often pose significant barriers to effective learning. *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* encourages active learning and engagement as it encourages students to take ownership of their learning, which promotes long-term academic interest and motivation. Other than that, this tool enhances knowledge retention and conceptual understanding. The process of continuous reinforcement and application of knowledge is a critical factor in the success of *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* as it enhances student learning outcomes. Besides that, this learning tool stimulates collaborative skill development. The game format naturally emphasises teamwork, as students work in groups to solve complex building services problems. This structure mimics real-world project settings, fostering critical collaborative skills such as communication, time management, and role allocation. Other than these advantages and positive impacts, *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* also has added value. *EZ.BAH Building Simplified's* adaptable framework suggests it could be applied to other technical fields and subjects where engagement and conceptual understanding are challenging. While the short-term benefits of *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* are evident, and examining its long-term impact on knowledge retention and professional readiness could offer further insights. Tracking how students learned via *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* performing in later but more advanced modules or in professional internships could help confirm the method's effectiveness over time.

Further development of this tool includes the potential to digitize parts of *EZ.BAH Building Simplified*, primarily through virtual or augmented reality, to extend its reach and make it accessible remotely, broadening its utility beyond traditional classroom settings. This could be especially valuable when in-person or when hands-on resources are limited. Another consideration is the ongoing development of content to align with advancements in building services' technologies and practices. As the industry grows more complex, incorporating the latest building systems or sustainability

standards into *EZ.BAH Building Simplified* would ensure it remains relevant and reflects current industry standards.

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